

Climatic and cryoclimatic indices, historical trends (1993-2022) and 2050 projections (Supplementary to 'Redistribution of frost weathering across Spain under recent climate warming')

This repository provides the supporting data and visualizations for the research article: "Redistribution of frost weathering across Spain under recent climate warming"

Overview

This dataset includes climatic and cryoclimatic indices derived from weather station data provided by AEMET (Spanish State Meteorological Agency). It covers historical observations from 1993 to 2022 and projections for the year 2050.

File Contents

Maps: Folder containing 13 high-resolution maps showing:

- Geographic distribution of climate types.
- Distribution of cryoclimatic indices.
- Observed trends (1993-2022).
- Future projections (2050).

Indices_Data.xlsx: A structured Excel file containing the raw numerical indices per station (AEMET codes included).

Contact

For questions regarding the data or methodology, please contact:

Javier Martínez-Martínez (Instituto Geológico y Minero de España, IGME-CSIC):
Javier.martinez@igme.es

Carlos G. Morales (Universidad de Valladolid): carlos.morales@uva.es

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